

CACTUS Policy Brief (D6.5)

Bridging the Gaps: EU–LATAM Cooperation and Long-Term Support for PV Research Infrastructures

INTRODUCTION

CALL: HORIZON-INFRA-2023-DEV-01-06

TOPIC: Research Infrastructures – Development (INFRADEV)

PROJECT: Enhanced solar photovoltaic performance through improved research infrastructure for adapted climate conditions (CACTUS).

CACTUS is a 2-year research and innovation project funded by the European Commission through the European Research Executive Agency (REA) grant N°101132182, responding to the call HORIZON-INFRA-2023-DEV-01-06.

CACTUS aims to develop a bi-regional and sustainable ecosystem of complementary RIs, strengthening the knowledge and collaboration between the EU and LAC regions, by enabling the research of solar and photovoltaic technologies adapted to different climate conditions. CACTUS will contribute to the green energy transition by tackling global challenges linked to energy and climate change (both mitigation and adaptation) with the provision of R&D tools for reliable, bankable, sustainable and socially accepted solar technologies.

CACTUS is formed of a multi-disciplinary consortium: 9 partners, consisting of one European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) and two Landscape European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI), three research centres, and one SME, additionally, two partners are from Latin American countries; covering the whole value chain of innovation from research centres to technology providers, end-users and market and policies.

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POLICY IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Implementation of research infrastructures

CACTUS has enhanced bi-regional integration of PV-relevant RIs by strengthening links between European infrastructures (CEA, ESRF, ILL, EURAC, TECNALIA) and LATAM partners (ATAMOSTEC, UNC). Although the project did not directly build new infrastructures, it fostered shared indoor–outdoor methodologies, strengthened data governance and revealed complementary capabilities across regions. The work contributes indirectly to future implementation of RIs in LATAM by demonstrating the value of long-term monitoring, harmonised protocols and access to advanced characterisation services.

Remaining bottlenecks:

- Lack of long-term OPEX funding to ensure continuity of monitoring and data quality.
- Fragmented frameworks for EU–LATAM joint RI planning.
- Limited visibility of European large-scale infrastructures (e.g., ESRF, ILL) to LATAM researchers.

Policy message: Support instruments enabling durable EU–LATAM RI collaboration and shared access frameworks.

RECOMMENDATION 1.1: Multi-annual EU and bi-regional funding frameworks should support the long-term operation, maintenance and upgrade of designated reference PV monitoring infrastructures. These frameworks should include dedicated OPEX budget lines and explicitly recognise the research teams responsible for sustaining high-quality, long-term reliability evidence and consistent datasets.

2. Access to research infrastructures

A key CACTUS contribution relates to building awareness and facilitating access to European world-class analytical infrastructures such as ESRF and ILL, whose capabilities for atomic-level, non-destructive characterisation are highly relevant for PV reliability research. Through joint work under WP2 and WP3, CACTUS enabled LATAM partners to become familiar with synchrotron radiation and neutron scattering as tools for inspecting material microstructure, degradation pathways, encapsulation interfaces and device-level failure modes—analyses typically unavailable in LATAM.

The project therefore broadened the user community by exposing non-EU researchers to unique European RIs and by discussing access mechanisms suited for third-country researchers. This form of early engagement is essential for creating future transnational access pathways and for positioning ESRF/ILL as reference infrastructures for climate-specific PV performance and materials research.

RECOMMENDATION 2.1: Ensure that future EU–LATAM cooperation instruments explicitly support access of non-EU researchers to European analytical infrastructures and encourage tailored onboarding mechanisms for industrial and academic users working on climate-relevant PV reliability challenges. EU research programmes should further boost impact by promoting access pathways for non-EU researchers—especially those in LATAM—who seek to use European large-scale infrastructures for material-level PV diagnostics. GREATER visibility of ESRF/ILL capabilities in the global PV community would multiply the effect of CACTUS outcomes.

3. Funding of research infrastructures

CACTUS highlights a systemic challenge: PV reliability and climate-specific degradation studies require robust long-term (5–10+ years) monitoring. Robust, long-term monitoring of PV systems is essential to understand reliability, degradation mechanisms, failure modes and operational risks of new PV cells, modules and systems. Monitoring periods of at least 5–10 years are typically needed to capture representative performance under real operating conditions, including evolving climate stressors and infrequent events to correctly evaluate reliability, understand failure modes and assess optimal operation and maintenance strategies to ultimately improve bankability and reduce associated risks.

However, most funding schemes for PV research infrastructures remain organised around project-based CAPEX and short-term OPEX. Equipment, instruments and installation are funded through research projects, while OPEX (staff time, maintenance, calibration, repairs, data acquisition and management) is covered only during the project lifetime, often corresponding around one year of post-commissioning data.

This creates a structural mismatch: long-term reliability questions require multi-year datasets, yet funding rarely supports data continuity beyond the project horizon. Monitoring campaigns are interrupted or scaled down, data quality erodes due to under-resourced maintenance, and the value of public CAPEX investments is not fully realised. The absence of stable instruments dedicated to multi-annual operation, maintenance and upgrade of PV research infrastructures represents a clear and important policy gap.

This mismatch between short project cycles and multi-year monitoring needs is directly relevant to Horizon Europe Research Infrastructures priorities on long-term sustainability of RI services and data continuity, as also reflected in ESFRI's emphasis on durable, high-value infrastructures. Addressing it is a condition for delivering bankable evidence at scale, which the EU Solar Strategy and REPowerEU depend on to achieve rapid PV deployment while maintaining reliability under climate stress.

Overarching Policy Recommendation 3: Establish a stable funding framework supporting the long-term operation and maintenance of PV research infrastructures.

RECOMMENDATION 3.1 – Create long-term O&M funding windows for reference PV infrastructures. EU and LATAM programmes should introduce dedicated windows for multi-annual CAPEX and OPEX of PV research and monitoring infrastructures, allowing 5–10+ years of support where reliability questions require it. A limited number of EU–LATAM reference infrastructures should be designated as eligible, with performance criteria on data continuity, quality, openness and external industrial use.

RECOMMENDATION 3.2 – Designate and support reference infrastructures and associated research teams. EU and LATAM public authorities should identify reference PV infrastructures and teams as strategic assets for climate-relevant PV research. Funding should prioritise these assets for long-term O&M support and recognise both physical infrastructure and key human capacities, including field performance monitoring and market-ready services such as digital twins and harmonised PV–climate datasets.

RECOMMENDATION 3.3 – Encourage long-term sustainability and skills roadmaps through funding incentives. Public funders should encourage operators to develop 5–10-year sustainability and skills roadmaps by providing targeted support actions and positive weighting in proposal evaluation. This improves planning for OPEX needs, upgrades and staff competences without imposing unrealistic eligibility burdens.

4. International co-operation of research infrastructures

Since 2019, EU and Latin American partners have collaborated to understand PV performance in harsh desertic and other non-conventional environments, generating insights relevant for LATAM deployment and for European strategies on reliability, bankability and long-term operation under a changing climate.

Stakeholders in both regions identify priority needs requiring bi-regional cooperation (D6.4), including accelerated ageing and climate-specific performance, climate-adapted bills of materials, optimised O&M and soiling mitigation, resilience to extreme weather, and improved access to climate-specific testing facilities and standards.

CACTUS capacity mapping (**D4.1**) shows that stronger funding constraints in LATAM push cooperation towards market-ready services (e.g. digital twins and harmonised PV–climate datasets) and highlights complementary strengths: EU partners lead in advanced reliability/testing and sustainability, while LATAM partners emphasise field reliability and deployment-oriented services. Better alignment of funding instruments and reduced structural barriers would support a more integrated, climate-relevant PV research ecosystem.

Despite early progress, cooperation **remains project-based, with no overarching EU–LATAM framework to coordinate joint infrastructures, data governance, shared access, standardisation or long-term monitoring**. Establishing such a framework would align with Horizon Europe objectives on the international dimension of research infrastructures and with the EU–LAC Global Gateway Investment Agenda, providing a concrete implementation pathway for PV reliability cooperation.

Overarching Policy Recommendation 4: Strengthen EU–LATAM collaboration to trigger synergies and reinforce research across different climate conditions.

RECOMMENDATION 4.1 – Establish an EU–LATAM PV Performance, Data and Capacity Partnership. EU institutions with LATAM regional bodies should formalise a partnership to coordinate bi-regional priorities on PV reliability under diverse climates, oversee shared infrastructures and data, and align agendas with stakeholder needs, building on complementary capacities.

RECOMMENDATION 4.2 – Fund multi-climate sister-site networks and structured EU–LATAM training programmes. Future EU–LATAM calls should support networks of sister sites across desert, tropical, temperate and high-altitude climates, embedding long-term monitoring components aligned with Policy Recommendation 3. Calls should allocate dedicated resources for recurring joint training and mobility focusing on data/reliability competences (predictive analytics, machine learning), advanced characterisation and sustainability skills in LATAM, and interdisciplinary profiles linking materials, devices, systems and climate data.

5. Employment and skills in research infrastructures

CACTUS has identified clear asymmetries: both EU and LATAM research centres report solid expertise in PV performance analysis, climate-related field monitoring, modelling and laboratory testing, but asymmetries persist. Advanced reliability/testing, PV cell device physics and sustainability profiles are more embedded in EU organisations, while LATAM centres emphasise field reliability, performance monitoring and deployment-oriented services. Bridging these asymmetries requires sustained training, mobility and data-centred skills development. Policy instruments should therefore reinforce data-centric competences (especially predictive analytics and machine learning), support advanced characterisation and sustainability capacities in LATAM, and promote interdisciplinary profiles bridging materials, device physics, systems and climate data.

Targeted bi-regional training and mobility instruments, as proposed here, align with Horizon Europe RI priorities on skills development and with the EU Solar Energy Strategy's focus on strengthening the solar ecosystem, including reliability and digital competences. They also complement the EU–LAC Digital Alliance by enabling joint development of harmonised PV-climate datasets and digital-twin services

POLICY RECOMMENDATION 5.1: EU and LATAM funders should provide dedicated, recurring capacity-building and mobility tracks within EU–LATAM PV infrastructure calls, with simplified rules and targeted support to counterbalance LATAM funding constraints and administrative barriers.

6. Greening of research infrastructures

No specific highlight at this stage.

7. Interaction of research infrastructures with industry

CACTUS shows that PV research infrastructures can provide industry with high-value services, notably long-term climate-specific performance and reliability datasets, interoperable monitoring/O&M tools and inputs to harmonised test and assessment protocols. These services support bankability, risk management and technology qualification for deployment under harsh and changing climate conditions.

By linking RI services to market needs, this contribution is consistent with the objectives of the EU Solar Energy Strategy and the Net-Zero Industry Act, particularly regarding reliable deployment and resilient value chains.

Key policy recommendation (R7.1)

Policy-makers should develop public–private co-funding instruments that enable industry engagement in long-term monitoring, climate-specific testing and the development of digital reliability services at research infrastructures, with clear conditions on data governance and access to maximise public value.

8. ERIC legal framework

Not applicable in the context of CACTUS. No issues encountered regarding EU-SOLARIS ERIC participation.

9. Technology development, data and digital services, digitalisation

CACTUS contributes substantially to technology development and digitalisation across several dimensions. First, the project advances **climate-specific test methodologies**, supporting future evolution of international standards (e.g. IEC) and improved module/material design for reliability. Second, CACTUS partners participated in The International Spectroradiometer Intercomparison (ISRC – European Commission, JRC Ispra), which forms a basis for future replication activities in LATAM to strengthen measurement harmonisation. Third, CACTUS introduces major digitalisation advances through harmonised datasets, the PostgreSQL-based **CACTUS Data Platform**, and improved digital O&M tools.

These developments support more predictive and data-driven PV operation, enable more accurate climate-specific modelling and pave the way for data-rich RI services aligned with EU digitalisation priorities.

10. Level of connection of your RI to EOSC

Limited relevance. No direct EOSC integration was in scope, although CACTUS adopts FAIR principles and provides an interoperable dataset architecture that can be aligned with EOSC-compatible frameworks in future EU–LATAM collaborations.

11. Contribution to other research areas and to broader EU priorities

CACTUS supports broader EU priorities—including REPowerEU, the EU Solar Strategy, the Net-Zero Industry Act and the Global Gateway Investment Agenda—by strengthening the evidence base for reliable PV

deployment under diverse and increasingly extreme climate conditions, and by reinforcing EU–LATAM research infrastructure cooperation.

The climate-specific approach used in CACTUS—combining field monitoring, advanced characterisation, standardisation insights and sustainability assessment—can also inform reliability and resilience research in other climate-exposed clean-energy domains (e.g. wind, concentrated solar power, green hydrogen and grid infrastructure), contributing to wider EU climate adaptation and competitiveness objectives.

12. Sustainability of research infrastructures

The sustainability of PV monitoring infrastructures is threatened by the CAPEX-centred funding model. Ensuring multi-annual OPEX support is consistent with Horizon Europe and ESFRI sustainability priorities for research infrastructures, and underpins the long-term evidence base required for reliable PV deployment under the EU Solar Strategy. Without reliable multi-annual OPEX support, infrastructures risk becoming under-utilised, long-term datasets remain incomplete, and staff retention and upgrade cycles are undermined.

POLICY RECOMMENDATION 12.1: Implementing multi-year OPEX support mechanisms for designated reference infrastructures, consistent with Policy Recommendation 3, to ensure data continuity and expertise persist beyond individual projects.